

1 Compressible gas flow in porous media characterized through a
2 compressibility number Π and pressure curvature

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6 **Abstract**

7 We analyze single-phase, isothermal gas flow in 1-D homogeneous porous media through a
8 pressure-squared porous-medium equation (PME). Non-dimensionalizing the PME with a steady
9 advective time scale exposes a compressibility number Π that measures relative pressure change
10 across the domain and parametrizes a family of globally attracting equilibria. We examine steady
11 and transient gas flow behavior across six decades in Π and three inlet boundary flow data, namely,
12 pressure, volumetric flux or mass flux, while keeping the pressure fixed at the outlet. At steady
13 state, we derive explicit relations linking different inlet data to a target Π , thereby selecting the
14 equilibrium pressure profile, the latter featuring a boundary layer of width $\propto \Pi^{-1}$, toward the
15 low-pressure outlet boundary, where the volumetric flux overshoots and the gas expands at a
16 rate $\propto \Pi^2$. For transients, high-resolution numerical simulations provide diffusion times based
17 on the L^2 -norm decay of the pressure toward its steady-state. We compare these observed times
18 against the slowest-decaying mode time of the eigenfunction expansion of the diffusion operator,
19 evaluated using a time-dependent effective diffusivity obtained as the harmonic mean of the local
20 diffusion coefficient. Close agreement identifies regimes where this scalar reduction captures the
21 variable-coefficient dynamics while systematic deviations quantify when spatial variability signifi-
22 cantly alters the path to the attracting equilibrium and a constant-coefficient surrogate fails. We
23 finally assess transient gas compression via pressure curvature. Differentiating the PME we obtain
24 an advection-diffusion-reaction (ADR) evolution for the curvature that explains the emergence,
25 migration, and sharpening of a curvature front. The proposed Π -curvature framework provides a
26 compact and operational lens to characterize compressible gas flows.

27 **Keywords** Flow compression, gas flow, porous medium equation

28 **1 Introduction**

29 Gas flow through porous media occurs in countless natural and industrial settings, including volcanic
30 degassing (e.g., *Massol and Jaupart*, 1999; *Oppenheimer et al.*, 2013), lake sediment venting (e.g.,

31 *Scandella et al.*, 2016), underground storage of natural gas (e.g., *Tek*, 1989), hydrogen (e.g., *Heine-*
32 *mann et al.*, 2021) and carbon dioxide (e.g., *Bachu*, 2008), air-based groundwater remediation (e.g.,
33 *Hunt et al.*, 1988; *Hu et al.*, 2010), and operation of membrane fuel cells (e.g. *Lee et al.*, 2019). In most
34 such settings, gas compressibility strongly affects transient and steady state flow behavior, leading to
35 a nonlinear relationship between the gas injection or pumping rate and the spatio-temporal evolution
36 of pressure and flow velocity. A notable example is large-scale gas reservoir operations, where gas is
37 periodically injected and pumped at different rates and through different prescribed boundary con-
38 ditions, namely, pressure, volumetric flux or mass flux, which causes qualitatively distinct transient
39 paths of the reservoir’s pressure toward its steady-state. How such paths differ as a function of the
40 type and intensity of the forcing through gas compression is not well characterized. Further, there is
41 no single operational measure quantifying the relevance of compression effects at the reservoir-scale.

42 Gas flow in porous media is generally described by combining mass and momentum (e.g., Darcy’s
43 law) conservation equations, and an equation of state (e.g., *Liepmann and Roshko*, 2001). The resulting
44 system is highly nonlinear, admitting analytical treatments only for few special cases (e.g., *Bear*, 1972).
45 This is because of the many gas flow parameters depending on pressure, namely, gas density, viscosity,
46 temperature and compressibility factor, the latter measuring departure of the gas from ideal behavior
47 (e.g., *Chen et al.*, 2006; *Chen*, 2007). However, for many practical cases, the pressure dependence of the
48 gas density dominates over the other parameters, which can be safely assumed constant. For such case,
49 the governing system reduces to a porous-medium equation (PME), written in terms of the pressure
50 squared and featuring a pressure-dependent diffusivity (e.g., *Al-Hussainy et al.*, 1966; *Vázquez*, 2007).

51 The PME is well known across disciplines concerned with the study of gas flow, including hydroge-
52 ology (e.g., *Baehr and Joss*, 1995), low (tight) permeable media, (e.g., *Wu et al.*, 1998; *Monteiro et al.*,
53 2012; *Wu et al.*, 2014; *Zhao et al.*, 2016), fluid mechanics (e.g., *De Socio and Marino*, 2006), petroleum
54 engineering (e.g., *Chierici*, 2012) and pure mathematics (e.g., *Vázquez*, 2007). Notable advances come,
55 on the one hand, from petroleum engineering literature, that considered the PME early on (e.g. *Muskat*,
56 1934, 1937), in combination with transformations such as the pseudo-pressure or pseudo-time to model
57 the flows of real gases (e.g., *Al-Hussainy et al.*, 1966; *Aanonsen*, 1985). Here, the PME is typically
58 linearized at some representative value of gas diffusivity (e.g., at mean pressure), enabling analyti-
59 cal treatment of well tests interpretation, average pressure forecasting and pressure buildup analyses,
60 among other numerous applications (e.g., *Matthews et al.*, 1967; *Tek*, 1989; *Chierici*, 2012; *Patzek*
61 *et al.*, 2013; *Ahmed*, 2018). However, these approaches are typically not concerned with resolving the
62 detailed spatial structure of the pressure field and its evolution, but focused on aggregated reservoir
63 behavior, and, consequently, do not explicitly address the nonlinear impact of gas compressibility in
64 the flow behavior. On the other hand, the mathematical analysis of non-linear diffusion equations
65 continuously investigates the PME from a theoretical viewpoint, reporting classical results concerning
66 finite-speed propagation (e.g., *Martinson*, 1976), self-similar solutions (e.g., *Aronson and Graveleau*,
67 1993; *Barenblatt*, 2003), degenerate diffusion (e.g., *Burgers*, 2013), geometrical properties of solutions
68 of the PME (e.g., *Lee and Vázquez*, 2003), and regularity of free boundaries (e.g., *Daskalopoulos and*

69 *Hamilton*, 1998). However, these analyses are rarely connected to operational contexts of applied fluid
70 mechanics or subsurface engineering, offering little practical guidance or physical insights on how the
71 global compression state affects gas flow evolution as a function of input boundary flow controls. De-
72 spite extensive work across petroleum, fluid mechanics and PME-specialized mathematical literature,
73 there is, to our knowledge, no framework systematically quantifying the impact of gas compression
74 effects on emergent gas flow behavior across operational boundary conditions at the reservoir scale.

75 Here, to progress toward the goal of having a global framework to interpret gas flow under variable
76 compression effects and boundary conditions, we introduce a compressibility number, Π , which non-
77 dimensionalises the pressure-squared PME and measures the strength of gas compression across the
78 domain via the relative pressure change between the initial and steady states. The parameter Π
79 is conceptually related to the compressibility number recently introduced by *Cuttle and MacMinn*
80 (2023), used to model gas-liquid displacement in a capillary tube and measuring gas compression
81 relative to viscous dissipation effects. In contrast, the present work focuses on single-phase gas flow at
82 the continuum scale, where compressibility affects transient storage and pressure diffusion rather than
83 interfacial displacement. The parameter Π provides a single yardstick linking steady and transient
84 responses across boundary conditions. We first revisit steady solutions through the lens of Π to expose
85 an outlet boundary layer with width $\propto \Pi^{-1}$ where the gas increasingly expands at a rate proportional
86 to Π^2 , and we derive explicit inlet-data relations that select a targeted Π (i.e. a specific attracting
87 equilibrium). We then examine transients with high-resolution MRST simulations (*Lie*, 2019; *Lie*
88 *and Møyner*, 2021), extracting diffusion times from the L^2 -norm decay of pressure toward its steady-
89 state, and comparing them against the slowest-decaying mode time corresponding to the eigenfunction
90 expansion of the diffusion operator evaluated using a time-dependent effective diffusivity, obtained
91 as the harmonic mean of the (spatio-temporally variable) local diffusion coefficient. The comparison
92 delineates regimes where a constant-coefficient surrogate is adequate and where spatial variability in the
93 pressure-dependent diffusion coefficient reshapes the approach to steady-state. We finally use pressure
94 curvature as a diagnostic of flow compression. Differentiating the PME twice with respect to space
95 we obtain a curvature evolution equation with the form of an advection-diffusion-reaction equation
96 (ADRE) that explains the emergence, downstream migration, and sharpening of a curvature front.
97 We track the location, amplitude and integrated curvature associated with this front, demonstrating
98 how these metrics provide compact diagnostics for identifying gas compression and expansion flow
99 regimes.

100 The article is organized as follows. In Section 2 we present the governing equations for gas flow,
101 including the porous medium equation (PME). In Section 3 we introduce the compressibility number
102 used to non-dimensionalize the PME and the pressure curvature evolution equation used as diagnostic
103 of compression regimes. Section 5 analyzes steady- and transient gas flow behavior. Section 6 concludes
104 the article.

2 Governing equations

The laminar flow of real gases in porous media is described by the following set of equations with adequate initial and boundary conditions:

$$\frac{\partial \phi \rho}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{q}), \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{q} = -\frac{k}{\mu} \left[\nabla p - \rho g z \right], \quad (2)$$

$$\rho = \frac{pW}{RTZ}. \quad (3)$$

Equation 1 is a statement of fluid mass conservation in the absence of sources or sinks, with $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ the porosity, $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$ the fluid mass density (kg m^{-3}) and $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ the (volumetric) specific discharge (m s^{-1}). The fluid velocity $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}, t)/\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$. The product of $\rho \mathbf{q}$ defines the mass flux, $\mathbf{q}_m = \rho \mathbf{q}$ (in $\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). $\mathbf{x} = (xx, zz)^T$ represents the position vector in the 2-D domains used here. Equation 2, Darcy's law, is a statement of momentum conservation at the continuum scale, with $k(\mathbf{x})$, $\mu(\mathbf{x}, t)$, $p(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and g denoting, respectively, the intrinsic permeability of the medium (in m^2), the dynamic viscosity of the fluid (in Pa s), the phase pressure (in Pa) and the constant of gravity acceleration (in m s^{-2}). For gases, the permeability is in general dependent on the pressure (*Klinkenberg, 1941*), although here we consider it constant given the large confining pressures (e.g., *Wu et al., 1998*).

The equation of state 3 relates the gas density with its pressure, via the (average) molecular weight of the pure gas (mixture) W (kg mol^{-1}), the universal $R = 8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and the compressibility factor $Z(p)$, the latter measuring the deviation of a real gas (or mixture) from ideal behavior. Here, we use the Peng-Robinson relationship (*Peng and Robinson, 1976*) for establishing the value of $Z(p)$ as a function of the gas properties. This is detailed in Appendix A.

2.1 Gas flow equation

Combination of Equations 1-3 and a series of manipulations and assumptions, detailed in Appendix A, leads to the non-linear partial differential equation on the pressure-squared (e.g., *Al-Hussainy et al., 1966*; *Chierici, 2012*) describing gas flow in homogeneous porous media:

$$\frac{\partial p^2}{\partial t} = D \nabla^2 p^2, \quad (4)$$

where the non-linearity stems from the pressure dependence of the diffusion coefficient

$$D = \frac{k}{\phi \mu \gamma}, \quad (5)$$

127 via its thermodynamic compressibility γ_g given in isothermal conditions as:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_g &= \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial p} \Big|_{T=T_0} \\ &= \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{Z} \frac{\partial Z}{\partial p}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

128 Equation 4 assumes negligible gravity effects and that the product μZ is approximately constant
 129 within the pressure range considered (e.g., *Al-Hussainy et al.*, 1966). As we show in Subsection A,
 130 the second assumption holds for pressures below 15 MPa for hydrogen. Note that Equation 4 is an
 131 instantiation of the Porous Medium Equation (PME) for $m = 2$ (e.g., *Vázquez*, 2007).

132 3 Compressibility number Π

133 We now non-dimensionalize the PME Equation 4 as follows:

$$\frac{\partial p^2}{\partial t} = D \nabla^2 p^2, \quad (7)$$

134 where \cdot denotes dimensionless variables or operators, defined as:

$$\nabla^2 = L^2 \nabla^2, \quad p^2 = p^2/p_L^2, \quad \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}/L, \quad t = t/\tau_{\text{adv}}^\infty, \quad (8)$$

135 with L a characteristic spatial scale, taken as the horizontal length of the reservoir, and the char-
 136 acteristic pressure-squared p_L^2 taken as the initial mean reservoir pressure. The advective time-scale
 137 at steady-state $\tau_{\text{adv}}^\infty = u^\infty/L$ is given in terms of the characteristic flow velocity at steady-state,
 138 $u^\infty = (k/\mu)(\Delta^\infty p/L)$, where $\Delta p^\infty = p_0^\infty - p_L$ is the pressure difference between inlet and outlet at
 139 steady-state. From now on, we drop \cdot since we work in non-dimensional space throughout.

140 The non-dimensional diffusion coefficient D is given as:

$$D(x, t) = \frac{p(x, t)}{\Pi}, \quad (9)$$

141 where the parameter $\Pi = \tau_D/\tau_{\text{adv}}^\infty$ ($= u^\infty L/D$) is the Péclet number for pressure, comparing τ_{adv}^∞
 142 against the characteristic time for pressure to diffuse across L , $\tau_D = L^2/D$.

143 We show now that Π can be used as a measure of the degree of compressibility effects experienced
 144 by the system at steady-state. Indeed, substituting $u^\infty = (k/\mu)(\Delta^\infty p/L)$ and $D = k/\gamma\mu\phi$, one
 145 obtains:

$$\Pi = \Delta^\infty p \gamma. \quad (10)$$

146 Since the intrinsic thermodynamic compressibility of the gas γ has units of inverse pressure, Π expresses
 147 a relative pressure (or density) change at steady-state, hence giving an average compression degree
 148 at that state. Small (< 1) and large (> 1) values of Π indicate mild and strong compression effects,

149 respectively. Consequently, we label Π as a compressibility number, which is to be distinguished from
 150 γ (Eq. 6). In Subsection 5.1.1 we give operational definition for Π as a function of applied inlet flow
 151 data.

152 **3.1 Temporal re-scaling using effective diffusivity for 1-D media**

153 We consider a temporal re-scaling accounting for time-varying diffusivity as follows (e.g., *Crank, 1975*):

$$t(\tau) = \int_0^\tau D_{\text{eq}}(s) ds, \quad (11)$$

154 where the time-varying equivalent diffusivity $D_{\text{eq}}(t)$ is calculated as

$$D_{\text{eq}}(t) = \frac{1}{\langle R(x, t) \rangle_x}, \quad (12)$$

155 with $\langle R(x, t) \rangle_x$ the (spatial) arithmetic mean of the resistivity $R(x, t)$, the inverse of diffusivity $D(x, t) =$
 156 $p(x, t)/\Pi$. Time-series and transient results are considered in terms of the diffusion-scaled time variable
 157 $t(\tau)$.

158 **4 Evolution equation for the pressure curvature $\kappa = \partial_{xx}p$**

159 We now derive an evolution equation for the pressure curvature $\kappa := \partial_{xx}p$, which is zero in the
 160 incompressible flow limit and increases in amplitude with the degree of flow compression. Further, the
 161 sign of κ indicates either, ongoing expansion, for $\kappa < 0$ (i.e., $\partial_x q^v > 0$), or ongoing gas compression,
 162 for $\kappa > 0$ (i.e., $\partial_x q^v < 0$). Thus, we use κ as a diagnostic (signed) scalar of the compression state of
 163 the gas over the domain. Using the fact that $\partial_t(p^2) = 2p \partial_t p$ and $\partial_x^2(p^2) = 2[(p_x)^2 + p p_{xx}]$, we re-write
 164 Equation (7) as

$$p_t = \frac{1}{\Pi} [(p_x)^2 + p p_{xx}]. \quad (13)$$

165 Differentiating twice with respect to x , we obtain

$$\kappa_t = \frac{4p_x}{\Pi} \kappa_x + \frac{p}{\Pi} \kappa_{xx} + \frac{3}{\Pi} \kappa^2. \quad (14)$$

166 Equation 14 has the form of an advective diffusion reaction equation (ADRE), thereby featuring three
 167 distinct mechanisms that govern the transient evolution of κ . First, an advection term $\frac{4p_x}{\Pi} \kappa_x$, with
 168 velocity u_κ given as

$$u_\kappa = -\frac{4p_x}{\Pi}, \quad (15)$$

169 a diffusion term $\frac{p}{\Pi} \kappa_{xx}$, with coefficient D_κ given as:

$$D_\kappa = \frac{p}{\Pi}, \quad (16)$$

170 which has the same form as in Equation 7, and a nonlinear reaction term,

$$R_\kappa = (3/\Pi) \kappa^2 \quad (17)$$

171 (self-)amplifying $\kappa \neq 0$. In Section 5.2 we use Equation 14 to interpret transient evolution under
172 different boundary conditions.

173 Since κ behaves as a signed transported scalar (e.g., *Acheson, 1990; Saffman, 1992*), we consider
174 the evolution of the zeroth-order moment (e.g., *Taylor, 1950; Aris, 1956*) of its positive and negative
175 parts, respectively, $\kappa^+(x, t)$ and $\kappa^-(x, t)$, to characterize emergence and decay of compression and
176 expansion regimes across the system:

$$M_i^\pm(t) := \int d\kappa^\pm. \quad (18)$$

177 We also consider the point of maximum $\kappa^+(x, t)$:

$$x_{\text{peak}}(t) := \arg \max \kappa^+(x, t), \quad (19)$$

178 which we use to track the compression front migrating toward the outlet while the system converges
179 to its steady-state. We do not consider moments of order > 0 (e.g., a center of mass or spread)
180 because curvature mass is not conserved but lost early on toward the outlet boundary, leading to
181 systematic biases of higher-order moments. This is not an artifact but an intended feature of our
182 setting, designed to investigate gas flow behavior that converges toward a boundary-modulated steady-
183 state (Subsec. 5.1). A moment-based analysis of curvature evolution away from the influence of outlet
184 boundaries remains the topic of further research.

185 Finally, we emphasize that, unlike classical porous medium flows with compact support, where
186 the interface between regions of zero and positive "mathematical" pressure constitutes a moving free
187 boundary (e.g., *Daskalopoulos and Hamilton, 1998; Vázquez, 2007*), the present problem features
188 $p(x, t) > 0$ throughout and, consequently, it remains smooth. As a result, classical spatial derivatives
189 up to fourth order are well defined, permitting formal derivation of Equation (14). We also stress that
190 Equation 14 is a *diagnostic* evolution law, that is, derived under assumed knowledge of p and p_x , which
191 are predicted from the governing equation of the system, Equation 7.

5 Analysis of gas flow in terms of the compressibility number

Π and pressure curvature κ

We focus on 1-D linear gas flow over a domain of length $L = 1$, since our goal is to understand the relationship between imposed inlet boundary data and emergent flow behavior via the Porous Medium Equation (PME) across different Π -values. Thus, at $x = 0$ we will apply either pressure p_0 , volumetric flux q_0^v or mass flux q_0^m , while at $x = 1$ we fix the pressure at $p_1 = 1$ throughout.

5.1 Steady-state behavior

We start by examining steady-state behavior. Setting $\partial p^2/\partial t = 0$ in Equation 7 the governing Laplace equation in 1-D reads:

$$\frac{d^2 p^2}{dx^2}(x) = 0. \quad (20)$$

Integrating Equation 20 once and using the fact that $\Pi = \nabla p^2 L/2\rho_L \gamma$ (Eq. ??), we obtain:

$$\frac{dp^2}{dx} = -2\Pi, \quad (21)$$

Integrating again, the affine-form solution in terms of Π reads as:

$$p(x) = \sqrt{2\Pi(1-x) + 1}, \quad (22)$$

and the corresponding expressions for the non-dimensional volumetric and mass flux, respectively, $q^v(x)$ and $q^m(x)$, read:

$$q^v(x) = -\frac{\Pi}{p(x)}, \quad (23)$$

$$q^m(x) = \Pi. \quad (24)$$

where we have used the equality between non-dimensional pressure and density, that is, $p = \rho$, we have set the characteristic volumetric and mass flux scales as $q_c^v = (k/\mu)p_L/L$ and $q_c^m = (WKp_L^2)/(RT\mu L)$, respectively (Subsec. ??). Differentiating Equation 23 we obtain the spatial gradient of q^v or, equivalently, the pressure curvature $\kappa(x)$:

$$\kappa(x) = -\Pi^2/p^3(x). \quad (25)$$

Figure 1 features profiles of non-dimensional pressure, flow velocity and modulus of pressure curvature for $\Pi \in [0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100]$.

Figure 1: Profiles of (a) pressure p , (b) flow velocity q^v and (c) modulus of pressure curvature κ for Π -values of (light to dark blue) (0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100).

211 The pressure profiles feature a concave shape, with near-constant gradient toward the inlet and a
 212 steeper gradient approaching the outlet (Fig. 1a). Correspondingly, a near-uniform flow velocity q^v
 213 (Fig. 1b) is observed for $x \ll 1$, and an overshoot develops as $x \rightarrow 1$. The spatial heterogeneity in
 214 q^v accentuates with increasing Π and toward the outlet, which is reflected in a negative curvature κ
 215 of increasing amplitude (Fig. 1c) toward the outlet. Physically, it reflects that gas parcels undergo
 216 increasing volumetric expansion as they flow downstream, with q^v increasing toward the outlet to
 217 conserve the constant mass flux $q^m = \rho q^v$ over the profile at steady-state while the pressure decays
 218 due to the imposed outlet condition. To understand how the gas expansion increases and distributes
 219 over space, we study the curvature scaling for the limit $\Pi \gg 1$. We partition the domain into an
 220 interior region $[0, 1 - \delta_{\text{BL}},]$ and a thin outlet boundary layer (BL) $[1 - \delta_{\text{BL}}, 1]$ of width δ_{BL} . We define
 221 δ_{BL} by requiring that the pressure at the inner edge of the layer remains $\mathcal{O}(1)$ relative to its outlet
 222 value (e.g., *Bender and Orszag, 2013*), that is:

$$p(1 - \delta_{\text{BL}}) = c, \tag{26}$$

223 where c is an $\mathcal{O}(1)$ constant. Evaluating the steady solution (Eq. 22) leads to:

$$\delta_{\text{BL}} = \frac{c^2 - 1}{\Pi}, \quad (27)$$

224 showing that δ_{BL} shrinks as Π^{-1} . Now, in the interior region we have $p \sim \sqrt{2\Pi(1-x)}$ and thus

$$\kappa \sim \Pi^{\frac{1}{2}}(1-x)^{-3/2}. \quad (28)$$

225 In contrast, within the BL we introduce the stretched coordinate

$$\xi = \Pi(1-x) \quad (29)$$

226 such that ξ remains $\mathcal{O}(1)$ while δ_{BL} is $\mathcal{O}(\Pi^{-1})$. Using Equation 25, we then have:

$$\kappa = \frac{\Pi^2}{(1+2\xi)^{3/2}} \quad (30)$$

$$\sim \Pi^2. \quad (31)$$

227 Thus, increasing Π both strengthens and spatially localizes the curvature, at rates Π^2 and Π^1 , respec-
 228 tively. A numerical example choosing $c = \sqrt{2}$ in Equation 27, gives $\delta_{\text{BL}} \in [100, 10, 1, 0.1, 0.01]$ for the
 229 chosen Π -values. When $\delta_{\text{BL}} > 1$ it means that compressibility effects are weak and distributed over
 230 the entire domain, consistent with an almost linear pressure profile and negligible curvature. Only for
 231 $\Pi \gg 1$ does a spatially-localized outlet boundary layer emerge. Finally, combining (27) with $\kappa \sim \Pi^2$
 232 in the BL shows that the integrated curvature scales linearly,

$$\int_{1-\delta_{\text{BL}}}^1 |\kappa| dx \sim \Pi, \quad (32)$$

233 consistent with the linear growth of the outlet volumetric flux $q^v(1) = \Pi$ (Eq. 23), by construction.

234 5.1.1 Operational maps

235 Evaluating Equations 22-24 at $x = 0$, we obtain straightforward operational maps between adjustable
 236 inlet flow data, p_0 , q_0^v or q_0^m , and a given targeted steady-state gas compression quantified by Π :

$$p_0 = \sqrt{1 + 2\Pi}, \quad (33)$$

$$q_0^v = \frac{\Pi}{\sqrt{1 + 2\Pi}}, \quad (34)$$

$$q_0^m = \Pi. \quad (35)$$

237 We will use Equations 33-35 in Subsection 5.2, to compare transient evolution toward the same attract-
 238 ing equilibrium across different applied inlet boundary data. In the context of gas reservoir operations
 239 such maps can be useful to adjust a targeted mass flow of gas, which is the relevant inlet condition,

240 through pressure or volumetric flow, which are the typical realizable boundary flow controls. The
 241 inverse maps are:

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{2}[p_0^2 - 1], \quad (36)$$

$$\Pi = q_0^v{}^2 + q_0^v \sqrt{1 + q_0^v{}^2}, \quad (37)$$

$$\Pi = q_0^m. \quad (38)$$

242 In the following we will use Equation 36 as operational definition of Π .

243 5.2 Transient behavior

244 To study transient flow behavior, we perform gas injection experiments by imposing pressure p_0 ,
 245 volumetric flux q_0^v or mass flux q_0^m , using the operational maps between these data and Π (Subsec. 5.1.1)
 246 to sweep over a range of Π -values between 10^{-7} and 800. For this, we solve numerically the coupled
 247 system of Equations 1, 2 and 3, using the Matlab Reservoir Simulation Toolbox (MRST) (*Lie*, 2019;
 248 *Lie and Møyner*, 2021). We do not consider Π -values over 800 to stay within the range of validity
 249 of Darcy’s law and ideal gas behavior. Despite this, our results are generalizable for compressibility
 250 factors $Z \neq 1$, provided the Z -field varies little over space.

251 5.3 Evolving compressibility Π across boundary conditions

252 We first consider an operational definition of Π , $\Pi^*(t) = (1/2)[p_0^2(t) - 1]$ based on Equation 36, which
 253 gives a transient measure of the compression state of the gas in the domain. Figure 2 features $\Pi^*(t)$
 254 time-series until steady-state across boundary data.

Figure 2: Time-series of the transient compressibility measure $\Pi^*(t)$ for targeted compressibilities (horizontal black lines) Π equal to 0.01, 1 and 100, the latter achieved for imposed inlet (blue) pressure p_0 (green) volumetric flux q_0^v and (red) mass flux q_0^m via the operational maps of Subsection 5.1.1. Different boundary data lead to different $\Pi^*(t)$ -paths for to achieve the same target Π , reflecting different pressure redistribution for each case. The normalized time is given by Equation 11.

255 For $\Pi = 0.01$, the evolution of $\Pi^*(t)$ for applied inlet mass flux (red) q_0^m and (green) volumetric flux
 256 q_0^v is equivalent, reflecting negligible compression of the gas. As the applied q_0^m and q_0^v are increased
 257 to yield a larger Π -value via the operational maps (Subsec. 5.1.1), $\Pi^*(t)$ corresponding to q_0^v appears
 258 to sit increasingly below the $\Pi^*(t)$ associated to q_0^m . This is expected, since increasing q_0^v demands
 259 less inlet pressure to drive a given mass flux during the transient period, leading to smaller $\Pi^*(t)$.
 260 At steady-state, all pressures converge to the same p_0 , leading to $\Pi^*(t) \rightarrow \Pi$. For imposed pressure
 261 (blue), $\Pi^*(t)$ appears near constant throughout, except from an early-time short transient associated
 262 with the pressure build-up applied by the simulator.

263 5.4 Pressure, flow and curvature distributions across Π and inlet flow data

264 Spatial distributions of pressure, volumetric flux and mass flux resulting from the simulations are
 265 reported in Figure 3 at diffusion-scaled times t equal to 0.1, 0.2 and 1 at (low) $\Pi = 0.01$ and (high)
 266 $\Pi = 100$ for the three different imposed boundary data.

Figure 3: Profiles of (a)-(b) pressure, (c)-(d) volumetric flux and (e)-(f) pressure curvature as a function of distance x at three different diffusion-scaled times t (Eq. 11) equal to (dark to light) 0.1, 0.2 and 1, for (left column) $\Pi = 0.01$ and (right column) $\Pi = 100$. Blue, green, and red lines correspond to imposed inlet pressure, volumetric flux and mass flux, respectively. For (e)-(f) a symmetric log compression of the data is used for visualization of the vertical axes, while the labels are given in the original units.

267 For $\Pi = 0.01$, we have $p \sim 1$ (Fig. 3a), by construction (Eq. ??), and p evolves similarly when
 268 imposing a volumetric flux q_0^v (red) or a mass flux q_0^m (green), as already noted in Figure 2. At steady-
 269 state, p converges toward the same nearly-straight profile across different applied boundary data.
 270 Since $p \sim 1$, the PME Equation 7 behaves as a linear diffusion equation with coefficient $D \sim 1/\Pi$,
 271 which admits the classical analytical solution as an eigenvalue-eigenfunction expansion of the linear

272 diffusion operator (Subsection B). The associated transient distributions of flow q^v (Fig. 3c) and pres-
 273 sure curvature κ (Fig. 3e) exhibit smooth positive lobes that rapidly relax toward their corresponding
 274 steady-states already described in Subsection 5.1. For imposed pressure (blue) the lobes feature the
 275 largest amplitude, indicating higher compression. This occurs because imposing pressure at the inlet
 276 forces a steady-state value (i.e., at $x = 0$) right from the beginning, requiring Equation 7 a more abrupt
 277 adjustment compared to imposing a volumetric or mass flux, cases for which pressure progresses more
 278 gradually toward its steady state. In this sense, the pressure governed by Equation 7 appears to evolve
 279 along a path of minimal compression whenever possible. This intuition is formalized within the theo-
 280 retical analysis of nonlinear diffusion equations (e.g., *Otto*, 2001; *Ambrosio et al.*, 2005; *Villani*, 2021),
 281 where transient (pressure) states relax toward steady state by following a trajectory of steepest descent
 282 of an energy functional, the latter defined with respect to the Wasserstein metric between two pressure
 283 states (e.g., *Ambrosio et al.*, 2005), whose detailed definition lies outside the scope of the present work.
 284 However, how this least-compression-energy trajectory depends on the imposed boundary conditions
 285 in practical settings (e.g., heterogeneous porous media) does not appear, to the best of our knowledge,
 286 to be fully characterized.

287 Now, moving on to the case $\Pi = 100$, $p \gg 1$ and its evolution differs significantly across imposed
 288 boundary conditions (Fig. 3b). The p -fronts advance more compactly and relax at steady-state toward a
 289 well-pronounced concave shape. This is mirrored in q^v (Fig. 3d) as a shock-like advancing front. Under
 290 imposed pressure (blue) this effect is most pronounced, followed by the case of imposed volumetric flux
 291 (red) and lastly by mass flux (green). Correspondingly, the κ -distributions (Fig. 3f) feature sharper
 292 positive (i.e., compression) pulses that are smoothed while traveling toward the outlet.

293 5.5 Interpretation of gas compression effects via pressure curvature $\kappa =$

$$294 \quad \partial_{xx}p$$

295 We now examine how gas compressibility emerge and evolve over time, by considering time-series of
 296 the mass $M_i^{\pm}(t)$ of κ^+ and κ^- , and the point of maximum $\kappa^+(x, t)$, $x_{\text{peak}}(t)$ (Subsec. 4), featured in
 297 Figure 4 for $\Pi = 0.01$ and $\Pi = 100$ across the different inlet BCs. Reported curvature masses are
 298 normalized by Π .

Figure 4: Time-series of (a)-(b) pressure curvature mass $M^\kappa(t)$ and (c)-(d) position of maximum positive curvature $x_{\text{peak}}(t)$ for positive (solid lines) and negative (dashed lines) pressure curvatures, κ^+ and κ^- , respectively, for the different imposed flow data, namely, (blue) pressure, (green) volumetric flux and (red) mass flux, at compressibility number values given by (a)-(c) $\Pi = 0.01$ and (b)-(d) $\Pi = 100$. The colored dots indicate the time for which $M^{\kappa^+} \approx M^{\kappa^-}$, marking the transition from compression- to expansion-dominated flow regime. From such time on, we stop tracking $x_{\text{peak}}(t)$ since κ^+ -mass vanishes. The normalized time is given by Equation 11.

299 For imposed pressure, the mass of the positive curvature, M^{κ^+} , is the largest (solid blue, Fig. 4a),
300 indicating stronger compression, as already discussed for Figure 3. M^{κ^+} increases at a rate $\propto t^{0.5}$,
301 reaches its maximum at $t \sim 10^{-5}$ and decays at a rate $\propto t^{0.5}$ until the characteristic time τ_D (i.e., at
302 $t \sim 1$), when it drops sharply. The temporal scalings are consistent with the (diffusive) rate $\sqrt{2Dt}$
303 at which pressure penetrates the domain. Note the position of compression front $x_{\text{max } \kappa^+}$ (solid blue,
304 Fig. 4c) evolves at the same diffusive rate, but starts to move only for $t > 10^{-5}$, that is, after the
305 maximum compression is reached, indicating a compression storage period before propagation. We can
306 interpret such an accumulation by considering the terms of the curvature PDE, Equations 15-17. At
307 early times, the imposed pressure creates a pressure gradient, which is spatially-variable due to the gas
308 compressibility, that is, a small κ^+ appears near the inlet. This activates the nonlinear reaction term
309 $3\kappa^2/\Pi$, leading to growth of κ^+ , while κ_x^+ and κ_{xx}^+ are still too small to drive significant advection
310 $k_x 4p_x/\Pi$ or diffusion $k_{xx}p/\Pi$, respectively. At the maximum of M^{κ^+} , diffusion smoothing begins to
311 dominate, via growth of k_{xx} combined with the imposed p , and the accumulated curvature or com-
312 pression is progressively redistributed downstream. Meanwhile, the mass of negative curvature, M^{κ^-} ,

313 becomes $M^{\kappa^-} \approx M^{\kappa^+}$ (colored dots), indicating the transition from compression- to an expansion-
 314 dominated steady-state. Imposing fluxes, that is, p_x (red and green, Fig. 4a), leads to a growth of M^{κ^+}
 315 $\propto t^1$ via the reaction term, until $t \sim 10^{-5}$. A delay is also observed before the curvature peak begins
 316 its downstream motion (red and green, Fig. 4c) because, despite the advection term being active from
 317 $t = 0$, via imposing p_x , at such early stage the curvature field is still being formed by the reaction
 318 term so there is little κ_x^+ or κ_{xx}^+ to advect or diffuse, respectively. Once a sufficiently sharp κ^+ lobe
 319 has developed the advective term kicks in and $x_{\max \kappa^+}$ evolves $\propto t^1$. For the case $\Pi = 100$, M^{κ^+} grows
 320 at a non-monotonic rate, approximately $\propto t^1$ for $t < 10^{-6}$ and $\propto t^{0.5}$ for $10^{-6} < t < 10^{-5}$, maximizing
 321 again at $t \sim 10^{-5}$ and decaying $\propto t^{0.5}$ until $t \sim 1$, when the transition to negative curvature occurs.
 322 Non-negligible negative curvature mass is observed well before $t \sim 1$ (dashed line in Fig. 4b), indicating
 323 gas expansion regions during the transient period. Higher inlet pressure leads to stronger curvature
 324 diffusing rapidly away from the inlet, since the diffusion coefficient increases with pressure. At the
 325 same time, such an incoming curvature generated upstream must be accommodated at the outlet to
 326 enforce the Dirichlet boundary condition. For small Π this process is weaker and delayed. Using the
 327 signed curvature field and associated PDE (Eq. 14) provides a complementary interpretative frame-
 328 work to understand how gas compression and expansion distributes over space and time, for instance
 329 disentangling the concurrent effects of gas compression and expansion, which are not directly apparent
 330 using mass conservation and pressure-based analysis only.

331 5.6 Impact of spatially-variable pressure diffusivity on gas flow

332 We now examine the impact on pressure $p(x, t)$ evolution arising from spatial variability in the diffusion
 333 coefficient $D(x, t) = p(x, t)/\Pi$. For this we consider distributions of pressure calculated analytically,
 334 $p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t)$, through the classical solution of the linearized PME (Eq. 7), which is exactly valid for the
 335 case $p \sim 1$ (e.g., *Carslaw and Jaeger*, 1959; *Crank*, 1975):

$$p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t) = p_{\text{ss}}^2(x) + \sum_n A_n \phi_n(x) \exp[-\lambda_n t], \quad (39)$$

336 where $p_{\text{ss}}^2(x)$ is the steady-state p^2 distribution and the second term is the eigenfunction expansion
 337 of the residual satisfying homogeneous boundary conditions. The coefficients A_n are the projections
 338 of such residual onto the Laplacian eigenfunctions $\phi_n(x)$, with BC-dependent eigenvalues λ_n given
 339 by $\lambda_n = (n\pi/L)^2$ and $\lambda_n = [(n + 1/2)\pi/L]^2$ for imposed inlet pressure or flux, respectively. For
 340 more details please refer to Subsection A. Note that the variable t corresponds to time scaled by the
 341 equivalent diffusivity $D_{\text{eq}}(t)$ (Eq. 11). Consequently, $p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t)$ accounts for temporal but not spatial
 342 variability in diffusivity $D(x, t)$. Figure 5 features $p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t)$ (dashed lines) against the simulated
 343 p^2 -profiles.

Figure 5: Pressure profiles as a function of distance x at three different diffusion-scaled times t (Eq. 11) equal to (dark to light) 0.1, 0.2 and 1, for (left column) $\Pi = 0.01$ and (right column) $\Pi = 100$ for imposed (first row, blue) pressure, (second row, green) volumetric flux and (third row, red) mass flux. Solid and dashed lines indicate pressure profiles calculated numerically and analytically, respectively. The numerically-calculated profiles evolve according to a spatially- and temporally-variable diffusion coefficient $D(x, t) = p(x, t)/\Pi$, while the analytically-calculated ones evolve according to a time-variable equivalent diffusion coefficient $D_{\text{eq}}(t)$ given as the harmonic mean of $D(x, t)$.

344 As expected, the discrepancy between the simulated p^2 -profiles and $p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t)$ is negligible for
 345 $\Pi = 0.01$, but increases for $\Pi = 100$. Further, the error behaves differently depending on the applied
 346 inlet flow data. The analytical solution predominantly under- and overestimates the true distribution
 347 when applying pressure (blue) or volumetric flux (green), respectively, while for applied mass flux

348 (red), the bias is predominantly positive at early times and features mixed positive and negative biases
 349 toward later times.

350 To quantify the aggregated error in the analytical solution due to unaccounted spatial heterogeneity
 351 in the diffusivity $D(x, t)$, we consider the time-averaged of the residual energy, $\mu_e(t)$, defined as:

$$\mu_e(t) = \frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau e_{\Delta u}(t), \quad (40)$$

352 where the energy $e_{\Delta u}(t)$ of the residual difference $\Delta u(x, t) = u(x, t) - u_{\text{calc}}(x, t)$ is given by (e.g.,
 353 *Evans, 2022*):

$$e_{\Delta u}(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 [u(x, t) - u_{\text{calc}}(x, t)]^2 dx, \quad (41)$$

354 with the residuals defined as $u(x, t) = p^2(x, t) - p_{\text{ss}}^2(x, t)$ and $u_{\text{calc}}(x, t) = p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t) - p_{\text{ss}}^2(x, t)$.
 355 The variable τ indicates a generic time over which the integration is performed, selected such that
 356 $e_{\Delta u}(\tau)/e_{\Delta u}(0) < \epsilon$, where we choose $\epsilon = 0.01$. Assuming identical steady-states Equation 41 reads:

$$e_{\Delta u}(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 p^2(x, t) - p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t) dx. \quad (42)$$

357 Figure 6 reports $\mu_e(t)$ as a function of Π and applied inlet boundary flow data.

Figure 6: Time-average $\mu_e(t)$ of the residual energy $e(t)$ between pressure distributions calculated numerically ($p^2(x, t)$) and analytically ($p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t)$), the former accounting for spatially- and temporally-variable diffusivity $D(x, t)$, and the later using a time-variable equivalent diffusivity $D_{\text{eq}}(t)$, obtained as the harmonic mean of $D(x, t)$. The average is performed over the interval $[0, \tau]$, with τ defined in the main text. The black line indicates scalings.

358 The time-averaged residual energy increases with approximately $\propto \Pi^{3/2}$, indicating more cumulated
 359 error due to neglected spatial variability in diffusivity $D(x, t)$ with increasing Π .

360 As an additional diagnostic of cumulated error, we consider the characteristic diffusion time-scale

361 needed for the pressure to reach its steady-state, τ_D^{obs} , estimated from the numerical simulations as
 362 follows:

$$\tau_D^{\text{obs}} := \inf \left\{ t \geq 0 : \frac{e_u(t)}{e_u(0)} \leq \epsilon \right\} \quad (43)$$

363 with $e_u(t) = 1/2 \int_0^1 u(x,t) dx$, again choosing $\epsilon = 0.01$. That is, τ_D^{obs} marks the minimum time at
 364 which the energy residual, normalized by its initial (maximum) value, is at a l_2 -distance smaller than
 365 ϵ . We compare it against a calculated diffusion time-scale τ_D^{calc} , satisfying the same criteria given
 366 by Equation 43 but using $e_{u_{\text{calc}}}(t) = 1/2 \int_0^1 u_{\text{calc}}(x,t) dx$. Considering the analytical expression of
 367 $p_{\text{calc}}^2(x,t)$ via (Eq. 39), it is straightforward to show that:

$$t(\tau_D^{\text{calc}}) \approx \frac{\ln(1/\epsilon)}{\lambda}, \quad (44)$$

368 which corresponds to the time for which the slowest-decaying mode of $p_{\text{calc}}^2(x,t)$, $\exp[-\lambda t(\tau)]$ (Eq. 39),
 369 is $\leq \epsilon$ and λ corresponds to the lowest-order eigenvalue of the the expansion, which is $\lambda_1 = \pi^2$
 370 and $\lambda_0 = (\pi/2)^2$ for imposed pressure or flux, respectively. A more detailed derivation is given in
 371 Subsection A.

372 Figure 7 reports τ_D^{obs} and τ_D^{calc} normalized by $t_D^{\text{linear}} = \Pi$, the latter obtained by setting $p = 1$ in
 373 Equation 9.

Figure 7: Characteristic times τ_D for gas pressure to diffuse across a domain of length $L = 1$, normalized by the reference diffusive time $\tau_D^{pL} = (kp_L/\mu\phi)^{-1}$ at initial domain pressure p_L , as a function of Π . Two different diffusive times are reported, (dots) τ_D^{obs} , calculated empirically from numerical simulations, satisfying criteria of Equation 43 and (dashed) τ_D^{calc} , calculated such that it satisfies criteria given by Equation 44, based on the slowest-decaying mode of the eigenfunction expansion of the linear diffusion operator (Subsec. B).

374 For small targeted steady-state compressibility, that is, $\Pi \ll 1$, the predicted τ_D^{calc} sits at $0.467\tau_D^{pL}$
 375 for applied inlet pressure p_0 (dashed blue, Fig. 7) and at $1.866\tau_D^{pL}$ for imposed volumetric q_0^v or mass flux
 376 q_0^m (dashed green and red). Indeed, for $\Pi \ll 1$ the diffusivity D is $D \approx D_{pL}$, with $D_{pL} = kp_L/\mu$ and so

377 from the definition of the diffusivity re-scaled time (Eq. 44) we have that $t(\tau) \approx \tau D_{pL}$. Combining this
 378 with $t(\tau_D^{\text{calc}}) = \ln(1/\epsilon)/\lambda$, we have $\tau_D^{\text{calc}} = \ln(1/\epsilon)/D_{pL}\lambda$, yielding then $\tau_D^{\text{calc}}/\tau_D^{pL} \approx \ln(1/\epsilon)/\lambda$, which is
 379 equal to 0.467 and 1.866 when $\lambda = \pi^2$ (imposed p_0) or $\lambda = (\pi/2)^2$ (imposed q_0^v or q_0^m), respectively.
 380 For $\Pi \lesssim 10^2$, a good agreement is observed between τ_D^{calc} and τ_D^{obs} for the cases of imposed (blue)
 381 pressure p_0 and (red) mass flux q_0^m , indicating that the slowest-mode formula using a time-variable
 382 equivalent diffusivity $D_{\text{eq}}(t)$ can be used to predict diffusion time-scales over a domain with spatially
 383 variable local diffusivity $D(x, t)$. As $\Pi > 10^2$, stronger pressure gradients lead to highly non-uniform
 384 $D(x, t)$ and the slowest-mode estimate fed by $D_{\text{eq}}(t)$ increasingly over predicts τ_D^{obs} . For the case of
 385 imposed (green) volumetric flux q_0^v the discrepancy between τ_D^{calc} and τ_D^{obs} remains negligible until
 386 $\Pi \sim 1$, it increases and decays again for $\Pi > 600$. Such non-monotonic dependence on Π highlights the
 387 nonlinear dependence of the pressure evolution with the applied injection, which appears accentuated
 388 for the q_0^v -case. This remains to be further investigated.

389 6 Conclusions

390 We developed a compact framework for compressible, single-phase gas flow in homogeneous porous me-
 391 dia that (i) casts the dynamics in a pressure-squared porous medium equation (PME), (ii) introduces
 392 a compressibility number Π that provides a single scale for comparing flow regimes across different
 393 inlet flow data, namely, pressure p_0 , volumetric flux q_0^v or mass flux q_0^m , and (iii) uses pressure cur-
 394 vature as a diagnostic of gas compression. At steady state, closed-form solutions in terms of Π lead
 395 to simple operational maps from a targeted Π to inlet controls and show that compressibility concen-
 396 trates the pressure drop into an outlet boundary layer of thickness $\delta_{\text{BL}} \sim \Pi^{-1}$, with curvature scaling
 397 $|\kappa| \sim \Pi^2$, and integrated curvature growing linearly with Π ; these scalings quantify volumetric-flux
 398 overshoot. For transients, we measure the time to steady by tracking the decay of the L^2 -norm of the
 399 deviation of p^2 from its steady state, and we compare these measured times against predicted times
 400 based on the slowest-decaying mode fed by a scalar effective diffusivity (the harmonic mean of the
 401 field at each time). The comparison is accurate over wide ranges of Π and deviates in regimes where
 402 spatial variability in $D(x, t) \propto p(x, t)$ localizes gradients and invalidates a constant-coefficient surro-
 403 gate. Differentiating the governing PME yields an advection-diffusion-reaction law for the curvature,
 404 which explains the emergence, sharpening, and downstream migration of a curvature front; tracking
 405 its position, amplitude, and mass provides concise diagnostics of the transient. High-resolution MRST
 406 simulations across several decades of Π corroborate the steady scalings, the operational maps, and
 407 the conditions under which the slowest-mode reduction suffices. The proposed Π -curvature frame-
 408 work offers insights of compressible gas flows and suggests extensions to heterogeneous media, higher
 409 dimensions, and non-ideal gas properties, as well as opportunities to use curvature-based metrics for
 410 control and optimization of injection-withdrawal protocols.

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506 A Derivation of the porous medium equation (PME) and an- 507 alytical solution for the linear case

508 Combining Equations 1-3 and assuming $g = 0$, constant values for the temperature T , permeability k
 509 and porosity ϕ , it is straightforward to obtain (e.g., *Al-Hussainy et al.*, 1966):

$$\frac{\phi}{k} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[\frac{p}{Z(p)} \right] = \nabla \cdot \left[\frac{p}{\mu(p)Z(p)} \nabla p \right], \quad (\text{A.1})$$

510 which, assuming $Z(p) \approx Z_0$ and $\mu(p) \approx \mu_0$, and noting that $\partial_t p \equiv \partial_t p^2/2p$ and further that $p \nabla p \equiv$
 511 $p^2/2p$ (for $p \neq 0$), transforms into the PME. In non-dimensional form it reads:

$$\frac{\partial p^2}{\partial t} = D \nabla^2 p^2, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

512 with diffusion coefficient

$$D(x, t) = \frac{p(x, t)}{\Pi}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

513 For negligible spatial variability of $p(x, t)$, and hence $D(x, t)$, Equation A.2 admits an exact ana-
 514 lytical solution in terms of an eigenfunction expansion of the residual $u_{\text{calc}}(x, t) \equiv p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t) - p_{\text{ss}}^2(x)$,
 515 between a given transient state $p_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t)$ and the steady-state $p_{\text{ss}}^2(x)$ (e.g., *Carslaw and Jaeger*, 1959;
 516 *Crank*, 1975):

$$u_{\text{calc}}(x, t) = \sum_n A_n \phi_n(x) \exp[-\lambda_n t], \quad (\text{A.4})$$

517 where the projections A_n of $u(x, t)$ onto the Laplacian eigenfunctions $\phi_n(x)$ are given as:

$$A_n = \frac{\int_0^1 u(x, t) \phi_n(x) dx}{\int_0^1 \phi_n(x)^2 dx}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

518 with

$$\phi_n(x, t) = \sin\left(\sqrt{\lambda_n} x\right) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

519 and $\lambda_n = (n\pi/L)^2$ for imposed pressure at the inlet, and

$$\phi_n(x, t) = \cos\left(\sqrt{\lambda_n} x\right) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

520 and $\lambda_n = [(n + 1/2)\pi/L]^2$, for imposed volumetric or mass flux at the inlet ($n = 1, 2, \dots$). The variable
 521 t is a diffusivity-scaled time to account for time-varying diffusivity (e.g., *Crank*, 1975):

$$t = \int_0^\tau D(s)ds. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

522 We now define the calculated diffusion time-scale τ_D^{calc} in terms of the slowest-decaying modes of
 523 the eigenfunction expansion of Equation A.4, given for the eigenvalues $\lambda_1 = \pi^2$ and $\lambda_0 = \pi^2/4^2$, for
 524 the inlet Dirichlet and Neumann conditions, respectively. For this, let the residual energy be defined
 525 by (e.g., *Evans*, 2022)

$$e_{\text{calc}}(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 u_{\text{calc}}^2(x, t)dx \quad (\text{A.9})$$

526 From Equation A.4 we have, at late times, that $e_{\text{calc}}(t)/e_{\text{calc}}(0) \approx \exp[-\lambda_1 t]$. Thus, defining τ_D^{calc}
 527 such that $e_{\text{calc}}(t)/e_{\text{calc}}(0) = \epsilon$, τ_D^{calc} satisfies:

$$t(\tau_D^{\text{calc}}) = \frac{\ln(1/\epsilon)}{\lambda_1}, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

528 or λ_0 for the Neumann condition.

529 For non-negligible spatial variations of $p(x, t)$ and $D(x, t)$, $D(t)$ in Equation 11 is replaced by an
 530 equivalent value at each time, $D_{\text{eff}}(t)$, given by the harmonic mean over x , that is:

$$D_{\text{eq}}(t) = \frac{1}{\int \frac{dx}{D(x, t)}}. \quad (\text{A.11})$$

531 B Numerical simulations

532 We simulate hydrogen injection into hydrogen-saturated 1-D reservoirs by solving numerically the
 533 coupled system of Equations 1, 2 and 3 using the Matlab Reservoir Simulation Toolbox (MRST) (*Lie*,
 534 2019; *Lie and Møyner*, 2021). The reservoir has a length and height of 600 m and 1 m, respectively.
 535 The top and bottom boundaries are assumed impervious. We vary the boundary condition at the
 536 right side while we keep a constant pressure of $p_0 = 10$ bar, equal to the initial pressure distribution.
 537 The viscosity μ , temperature T and compressibility factor Z are assumed constant throughout, with
 538 values $\mu = 8.1 \times 10^{-6}$ Pa·s⁻¹, $T = 320$ K and $Z = 1$. The porosity is $\phi = 1$ throughout. The domain
 539 is discretized into 2400×1 cells, giving a cell size of 0.025 m.